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WATERMELON

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CULTIVATION PATTERN OF CUSTARD APPLE IN TAMILNADU

 Dr. A. DHARMENDRAN and P. ANDICHAMY

INTRODUCTION

Custard apple is one of the most delicious fruits. This crop is known by various names like sitaphal, sugar apple, sweet sop and sarifa. Its botanical name is *Annona squamosa* and it belongs to the family *Annonaceae*. Custard apple is a common cultivated crop in India, China, Philippines, Taiwan, Australia, and Cuba. The fruit has commercial importance in Egypt and Central Africa. Custard Apple has recently become very popular in certain regions of India, especially Tamil Nadu, Orissa, Assam, Rajasthan and Gujarat. The area under custard apple is reported to be more than 40000 hectare.

CLIMATE

Being a tropical crop, custard apple prefers dry climate. It can also be grown in middle subtropics. It can withstand mild frost but the fruits become hard and do not ripen in cold weather. It prefers dry climate, during flowering but the fruit set is aided by high humidity which begins with the onset of monsoons. Annual rainfall of 50 to 75 cm is optimum, though it can withstand higher rainfall or drought. In tropics, water stress puts this plant in quiescence while in sub-tropics low temperature and water stress in summer create these conditions which help this plant to withstand drought better and make it an ideal plant for arid horticulture.

SOIL

Custard apple is tolerant to any type of soil. It grows well in rocky as well as in sandy soils. In heavy soils also it grows well provided there is good drainage facility. It is rather a shallow rooted crop. It is tolerant to many soil conditions, except alkalinity.

VARIETIES

There are two main colour custard apples like 'Red fruited' and 'Green fruited'. Under these colours, the following varieties of custard apples were cultivated in Tamil Nadu.

1) Washington 107005, 2) Washington 98787, 3) Mammoth, 4) Balanagar, 5) Local Graft, 6) Red Sitaphal, 7) Barbados, 8) Atemoya, 9) British Guinea and 10) Christened 'APK (Ca) 1'.

PROPAGATION

Custard apple can be propagated through seeds and vegetative methods which are described hereunder :

a.i. **1. Seed Propagation:** Custard apple is generally grown from seeds. For arid conditions, seedlings are raised in pots or polythene bags filled with garden soil and are planted in the field at the onset of monsoon when they attain the height of 20-25 cm.

a.i.2. **Vegetative Propagation:** Vegetative propagation is gaining popularity now-a-days in custard apple. The different methods of vegetative propagation, stem cutting, enriching and budding are now used for multiplication of custard apple.

zi) **Cutting:** Custard apple is a difficult-to-root fruit plant, therefore, rooting does not occur easily. Under intermittent mist, 90 per cent rooting can be obtained with NAA (Naphthalene Acetic Acid) at 5000 ppm, when the shoots are etiolated for 15 days prior to planting.

ii) **Enriching:** Inarching seems to be the most successful method of vegetative propagation in custard apple. Side grafting is also practiced to get more advantages. Grafting has been found superior to budding.

iii) **Budding:** The common methods of budding practiced in custard apple are shield, patch, modified forkert and chip budding. Budding is usually done in early spring or in the autumn.

PLANTING

Pits of 60x60x60 cm size are made in summer, refilled with soil and Farm Yard Manure (FYM) in 1: 1 ratio. Planting distance is kept at 4.5x4.5 to 5x5 metre. Planting is done in the beginning of monsoon to avail the advantage of available rain water. On an average about 490 plants will be needed to cover a hectare.

FERTILIZER APPLICATION

In each pit, one or two baskets of well rotten FYM or compost is incorporated at the time of pit filling. A

fertilizer mixture of 250 g containing ammonium sulphate, superphosphate and muriate of potash is also mixed with the soil in every pit. These are applied in the beginning of monsoon. It has been observed that the plant responds better to organic growth. A study has indicated that application "of 250 g nitrogen, 125 g phosphorus and 125 g potash per plant gives maximum yield.

IRRIGATION

Custard apple does not require any irrigation and is able to produce a good crop without being irrigated provided effective water supply is ensured to the rhizosphere, (root zone) by developing micro-catchment in rainy season. However, in post-monsoon period 2-3 irrigations help in better quality fruits and higher production. Drip irrigation is the most efficient method to manage scarce water resource which can be created by harvesting run-off during monsoon in arid region.

TRAINING AND PRUNING

Newly planted grafts are trained to develop proper shape. A bearing custard apple tree is amenable to pruning and responds favorably in terms of better size of fruits. If left unpruned, it forms a bush with large number of branches. It will affect the yield of custard apple.

INTERCROPPING

In young orchards of custard apple, intercrops can be taken. It is only possible during rainy season for which chilies, beans, black-gram, red-gram, horse-gram, etc are recommended. In places where irrigation facilities are available, even winter vegetables can also be grown.

FLOWERING AND FRUITING

Both seedling and vegetative propagated plants come into bearing from 4-6 years. It takes another 4 to 5 years to produce an average yield. In sub-tropics flowering period extends from spring (February to March) to rainy season, while in tropics it is mainly governed by the availability of water. A medium size tree bears 1000-1500 flowers in a season and only 2-3 % flowers set and bear fruits.

INSECT PESTS AND DISEASES

Generally, custard apple is free from insect pests and diseases. Cracking of fruits sometimes occur due to poor water relations, which can be overcome by regulated water supply. Some important pests and diseases are given below.

1. Mealy bug (*Ferrica virgata*): This insect is very common. It can be controlled by spraying

Nuvacron or Phosphomidon at 10 ml per 10 litres of water.

2. **Anthracoze:** It is a fungal disease caused by *Glomerella cingulata*. This disease can be effectively controlled by three fortnightly sprays of Benlate 0.05 per cent from the beginning of initiation of symptoms.

3. **Leaf spot:** This is also a fungal disease caused by *Cercospora anonal*. This can be controlled by spraying copper fungicides at 0.1 per cent concentration. Bordeaux mixture is the most effective.

HARVESTING AND YIELD

Custard apple starts bearing at the age of 4 to 6 years and declines after 20-25 years. Harvesting may extend from September to November depending upon the period of flowering. This can be varied also. It is a climatic fruit and should be harvested mature which can be judged on the basis of change in colour between tubercles and their falling apart. They should be harvested firm for distant marketing. An average tree of custard apple yields 100-150 fruits per year, while bigger and vigorous tree may yield more and each fruit weighs about 0.120-0.230 Kg.

STORAGE AND MARKETING

Being a perishable fruit, custard apple cannot be stored for long period, and cold storage is not promising for custard apple. The hard fruit becomes chilled at 15.5°C or below. Though the ripe fruits can be kept for 6 weeks at 4.4°C, the skin becomes brown and unattractive. In India, custard apple fruits are sold locally due to their perishable nature. But in other countries, they are packed and transported to distant markets.

CONCLUSION

Custard apple cultivated in Tamil Nadu is mainly sent to Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Maharashtra. The profit from the sale of fruits mainly goes to growers, who use it for their development activities. The optimum productive life span of the variety is 25 years, according to scientists. The best season for planting is May-June, August-September. It yields about 7300kg fruits per hectare (14.90 kg per tree). It is suitable for cultivation in the plains of Tamil Nadu especially in semi arid regions and marginal soils of both vertisols and alfisols in dry tracts. It is suitable for both rain fed and irrigated conditions.

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